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CONTENT OF COMBINED PESTICIDES IN WATER, SHORELINE, AND BOTTOM SEDIMENTS OF THE RIVER ALAZANI

Abstract. Pesticide pollution of rivers from agricultural fields is a widespread problem. Pesticides accumulated in excessive amounts after rain will be washed into surface water bodies or seep into groundwater, as a result of which it is possible to deteriorate the ecological condition of rivers.

Although Georgia has approved the list of permitted pesticides defined by the Rotterdam Convention, which does not include pesticides containing dangerous chemical substances, in some cases they are still used by the population. This has a harmful effect on the environment (including water).

Based on the mentioned problem, we have studied the content of pesticides – DDT, Decis, and Belaphos in the water, coastal soil, and bottom sediments of the Alazani River of Eastern Georgia. Sampling was done in the fall of 2023 from 3 points selected as research objects (Akhmeta, Tsnori, Gurjaani). Based on the results of the research, we can conclude that the increased amount of DDT brought by water is observed in the soil of the river coast. As for Decese and Belaphos, their numbers were found in all three points. This indicates that due to the low sanitary education of the population, the rules of storage and use of poisonous chemicals are not being observed. Their excessive and uncontrolled use has a negative impact on the ecological condition of the river and its ecosystem. Therefore, it is of great importance to strictly observe the rules of use during its usage.

Key words: River Alazani, Pesticide Decis, Belaphos, DDT

Research goals and results: The goal of our research was to determine the content of combined pesticides Decis, Belaphos, and DDT in the water, coastal zone and bottom sediments of the Alazani River. Researches were conducted in 3 points (Akhmeta, Tsnori, Gurjaani) in the fall of 2023.

Pesticides have a negative influence on human health damaging the nervous system, and liver functioning, promoting cancer development, affecting reproduction and endocrinological systems, etc. The great number of fertilizers in reservoirs causes the accumulation of an additional amount of phosphorus and Nitrogen often causing eutrophication. As we know rivers flow by agricultural lands and, naturally, the normal eco condition of the river is affected by fertilizers used for agricultural purposes. Sometimes guidelines for pesticide use are ignored which has a negative effect on environmental components (including water). Hence, we decided to study the combined effects of those pesticides allowed by the Rotterdam

Convention and which are often used in violation of norms. These pesticides are Decis – pyrethroid organic fertilizer (P) and Belafos(Fop). It is known that nowadays, combined effects of pesticides are often used in agriculture for their toxic effect on flies. But we shouldn't forget that their intensified usage becomes more dangerous for humans and animals in the water. That is why we decided to study the combined effect of Delafos and Decis

The conducted studies showed that a greater amount of DDT brought by water appeared in the coastal soil of the river. As for Decis and Belaphos, they are found in all three regions studied by us. The combined effect of DDT, Decis, and Belaphos in the Alazani River and soil are given in Tables №1, 2.

Table 1

№	Place and time of sampling Autumn. 2023.	Pesticides		
		Decis	Belaphos	DDT
1	Akhmeta	0,012	0,0030	0,005
2	Tsnori	0,032	0,0036	0,007
3	Gurjaani	0,033	0,0054	0,008
MAC		0,05	0,006	0,1

Table 2

№	Place and time of sampling Autumn. 2023.	Pesticides		
		Decis	Belaphos	DDT
1	Akhmeta	0,008	0,059	0,009
2	Tsnori	0,008	0,078	0,010
3	Gurjaani	0,010	0,089	0,015
MAC		0,1	0,1	0,1

Increased combined effects of Decis and Belaphos are noticed in the bottom sediments. Though they do not exceed the permissible concentration limit but are significantly increased which is disturbing (table 3). Though the usage of DDT is prohibited, the period of its decomposition takes a long time, so its traces are still found in soil and bottom sediments.

Table 3

№	Place and time of sampling Autumn. 2023.	Pesticides		
		Decis	Belaphos	DDT
1	Akhmeta	0,097	0,019	0,011
2	Tsnori	0,149	0,167	0,078
3	Gurjaani	0,167	0,078	0,098

Conclusion. Thus, we can conclude that people actually neglect to keep to regulation norms on using pesticides, as the level of their sanitary education is low. Most pesticides are toxic for human beings and animals causing their involvement in the live systems food chain existing in the river. As for the combined effects of Decis and Belafos, they are neurotoxins and damage neurons, human memory and develop stress. So, it is essential to keep to norms of usage during their utilization.

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